

A Concise Historiography of Plague Epidemic in Colonial Bengal Since 1868 to 1947

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Abstract: During the course of colonial rule – the disease plague considered to be a very harmful catastrophe for the native people of this country. Frequent outbreak of plague harassed the natives and the colonial government and it caused huge mortality whenever it rapidly spread. In most of the historical writings on plague marked their starting point of analysis from Bombay plague epidemic in September 1896 but before Bombay, different parts of Bengal Presidency had already faced the evil effect of plague. This paper attempts to analyse how the epidemic of plague appeared and spread in Bengal Presidency since 1868 to 1947 and also the role played by the colonial government to eradicate the disease. The current study also revealed the impact of plague epidemic on socio-religious life of the native people of Bengal.

Key Words: Plague, Rat, Epidemic, Disease, Sanitation, Vaccination, Quarantine, India, Bombay, Bengal, Calcutta, Midnapore, Government, Native.

Prevalence of Plague

According to the report of W.W. Hunter, the Collector of Midnapore, cattle plague of a fatal character appeared in Midnapore – a large district of Bengal Presidency in 1868. The disease first broke out in the month of October and it became severe till January in 1869. It still prevailed up to the April 1869. From 1868 to the end of 1869 numberless people of Midnapore district suffered from plague and massive mortality occurred due to the lack of proper treatment. This was the earliest record of plague epidemic in Colonial Bengal. After 1869 to 1895, few cases of plague observed in the different districts of Bengal.¹ During colonial period, two factors were mainly responsible for the spread of plague; (i) The prevalence of excessive number of rats. (ii) Ill-ventilated and insanitary houses of the natives which were suitable abode for rats.²

A terrible epidemic of plague spread throughout Bombay Presidency in 1896 and total 1,936 deaths occurred. Next year in 1897 mortality increased to 11,003 only in Bombay Presidency and altogether 53,816 throughout India.³ Gradually it reached in Bengal. In Calcutta it observed in 1898 at British India Steam Navigation Company's dock.⁴ Within a few days the disease spread rapidly at Khidirpore. Instantly the Government deputed Captain W.A. Justice, the IMS officer to investigate the case. After

vivid investigation, Captain Justice reported that the reason behind the rapid spread of plague in Calcutta was rat infected grain and gunny bags. He reported, some days ago before the rapid spread of the disease, oilseeds imported at Calcutta through railway from Hyderabad. After a week numerous rats were found into the stocks of oilseeds. Through the rats and also by the grains plague was rapidly spread from one place to another.⁵ Therefore a controversy began among officials that who was responsible for the spread of plague in Calcutta and adjacent districts? Was it reached by sea communication or by railway communication? W.W. Clemesha, the Officiating Sanitary Commissioner of Bengal published an article in 1906, in the Indian Medical Gazette titled- "An Account of Plague in Bengal". In his article W.W. Clemesha claimed, plague reached in Calcutta by sea communication not by railway communication.⁶ Whereas Captain W.A. Justice, the then investigating officer of plague in Calcutta presented a paper in All India Sanitary Conference held at Bombay on 13th and 14th November 1911, titled "Passporting of Grain and Grain Gunny Bags from Localities Infected with Plague." In this article Captain Justice argued that plague reached in Calcutta through the imported oilseeds from Hyderabad by railway communication.⁷

Gradually, plague spread at Bali town. After that the disease reached at Cowl Bazar, where in some shops these oilseeds were gathered.⁸ W.W. Clemesha claimed, during the year 1898, plague spread from Calcutta to Hooghly, 24-Parganas, Mindapore, Burdwan etc.⁹ Huge mortality occurred in 1898 from plague not only in the different parts of Bengal but also in India. During the year total 1,16,285 mortality recorded throughout India and it increased to 1,39,009 in 1899. According to the report of Professor David Arnold, due to the spread bubonic plague, total 10 million people lost their lives across India between 1896 to 1921.¹⁰

The Sanitary Commissioner of Bengal reported in 1905 that, in Bengal the mortality from plague was great amongst the shopkeepers, sweetmeat vendors and grain-dealers. Plague appeared mostly in the dark ill-ventilated rat infected stores and godowns. Death rate was also high among the peasants. In rural Bengal it usually noticed that peasants gathered grains in their houses. Most of the houses were built of mud, bamboos and woods. Therefore rat abodes were common in houses like this. When peasants stored grains into their house, rats automatically attracted to eat the grains. Thus rats increased in numbers quickly.¹¹ The causative agent of plague is 'Yersinia Pestis' a bacterium found into the salivary glands of the rats. Therefore the peasants became easily infected by the plague.¹² Administration Report of Bengal for 1909-1910 revealed, due to the spread of plague, total 1,779 persons died in Calcutta in 1908 and in 1909 it increased to 1,915.¹³

Fluctuation of plague mortality was common in Bengal. In 1912 there were total 1,995 deaths recorded from plague throughout Bengal. In 1913 it decreased to 984 and in 1914 it more decreased to 554. Gradually the sever-

ity of plague had ebbing in Bengal. In 1915 total 199 deaths reported from plague throughout Bengal Presidency. During the year 1915 some cases of plague observed in Midnapore district but there were no deaths occurred.¹⁴ Few years after in 1925 only 9 cases of plague reported and all from Calcutta and death rate was just 001 per mile. Besides, during the year no deaths occurred in Midnapore.¹⁵ Actually the severity of plague was not observed in lower provinces of Bengal as it was observed in Calcutta or in Bombay. Contemporary census reports revealed that, Midnapore, Bankura and Purulia districts were free from severe plague epidemics since 1921 to 1947, but few cases observed almost every year.¹⁶

Anti-Plague Measures of the Government

Anti-plague campaigns initiated by the Government Bengal for each district through some steps i.e., (i) Rat killing measures were taken in the plague affected areas of the districts. (ii) Sprayed of paraffin (kerosene oil) into the huts, dwelling houses, cattle sheds, godowns, stores etc. (iii) Vaccination campaigns were performed.¹⁷ (iv) Admitted infected people at the hospitals either understand or by force. (v) Isolation of the infected people into the private house was made compulsory. (vi) Regular checked up of pilgrims and railway and seaway passengers.¹⁸

According to the Government officials, vaccination was only effective treatment against plague. Haffkine arrived at Calcutta from Bombay on 7th October 1896 and he started vaccination operation. Between January to July 1897, total 7,905 plague infected people were vaccinated by Haffkine and it was found effective.¹⁹ It observed from the Sanitary Commissioner's Report of 1900 that, plague identification camps were carried on for the railway passengers at Howrah, Sealdah and other big stations and also the steamer passengers at Khidirpur, Ghatal and Tamluk of Midnapore district.²⁰ Besides, the pilgrims of Midnapore district who about to attain Rathayatra festival at Puri and also those returned in Midnapore district from Puri, were forcefully medically examined.²¹

To control over the situation, The Epidemic Disease Act was passed in 1897. After that an order passed by the Government that, if deputed officers suspected any passenger of ports, railways and others had to be forcefully checked up by the health officers in-charge.²² Under Plague Regulation-A, dated the 8th October 1900; it mentioned that, if a case of plague might found in any house, the health officer should adopt necessary steps to disinfect the whole house and no obstruction would be allowed.²³ Under Plague Regulation-B, dated the 8th October 1900; it further stated that, if plague broke out in any cantonment or in municipal areas, the District Magistrate might issue the essential regulations to perform sanitary precaution measures. For example, washes of the houses with lime water, cleaning latrines, removal of filths etc.²⁴ Under Plague Regulation C, dated the 8th October 1900; again an order passed that the sub-divisional magistrate might engage medical officers or vigilance committee for villages and non-

municipal towns for the prevention of plague.²⁵

Besides, rat killing measures were carried on in Bengal. During the year 1907 total 1,22,090 rats killed throughout Bengal.²⁶ In 1908, a special plague conference was held at Patna by the ardent wish of the Lieutenant Governor of Bengal. According to the guidance of the conference, the Sanitary Commissioners distributed special leaflets in the different districts regarding plague awareness and translated it into some vernacular languages.²⁷ Herewith a massive rat killing measures were observed in Calcutta. During 1915, total 1,30,953 rats killed through the initiative of the Calcutta Corporation. Besides, the total numbers of dead rats removed by the corporation's engineer's staffs were amounted to 65,637. Apart from that, Rs.2,046 was paid during the year as rewards to the rat catchers.²⁸

Reaction of the Native People

Panic formed among natives by the anti-plague campaigns of the Government. Generally it assumed that if anybody infected with plague, he or she would be forcefully isolated and admitted to the hospital. It also believed that during illness or even till death, the patient would not be permitted to meet his or her family.²⁹ Actually, natives believed that their customs hindered through the anti-plague measures of the Government. Therefore, anti-vaccine movement was organised in Calcutta and in Kharagpur, a renowned town in Midnapore district. They burned dispensaries, destroyed the tubes of vaccine and attacked the railway tracks.³⁰ In 1897, W.C. Rand, the then Plague Commissioner of Pune was murdered by the angry natives.³¹ Besides, the natives believed more in worship of 'Plague Mata' for their cure than of vaccination. Plague Mata generally worshiped in Sitala temples. Whenever the Government forced the native people to accept and agree with the colonial methods of treatment, agitations formed because they felt that the Government forcefully interfered in their religious as well as social morals.³²

Observation

It is evident from the above discussion that, during colonial period plague considered to be a very a dangerous disease. It spread through infected rats. Since 1868 to 1947, plague spread not only in Bengal Presidency but also in the different parts of India. Though, its maximum severity was seen in Bombay and Calcutta during 1896 to 1898. It is notable that, during the course of colonial rule, Bombay and Bengal Presidency suffered most due to the plague epidemic than of other parts of India. But it can't be denied that more or less entire country frequently suffered from plague epidemic since the third quarter of the 19th Century. British Government formed Indian Plague Commission in 1898-1899 to inquire into the causes and the remedy of the disease under the leadership of Professor T.R. Fraser of Edinburg University, Mr. J.P. Hewett, the Secretary to the Government of India in the Home Department, Professor A.E. Wright, the Army Medi-

cal School in Netley, Mr. A. Cumine, the senior Collector of Bombay Presidency and Dr. Ruffer, the President of Sanitary, Maritime and Quarantine Council of Egypt.³³

After the vivid inquiry, the Plague Commission reported in 1901 that, through the infected rats; plague easily spread from person to person in the different localities of India by railways and seaways. The Commission suggested to the Government of India that forced quarantine and vaccination was needed to control over the disease.³⁴ Therefore steps were taken to contain the disease such as awareness programs, vaccination, isolation and quarantine either mutually or by force. But Government claimed that prejudices of the native people were the main barrier in the way of further improvements.³⁵ In the end it is essential to note down that the government initiated some anti-plague measures to control over the situation but more decent steps were needed to remove the disease from a crowded country like India. If prejudices of the natives became the main barrier in front of the government to remove the disease from localities, then indifferent health policy was also another barrier. As a result, lots of deaths and sufferings were seen among natives till Independence.

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